

Literature Review on Therapy Approaches as a Therapeutic and Developmental Tool for the Individual

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To cite this article: Soner Özkan, Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 123 – 146. - 0099-0001-2210-0104.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

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Abstract

Writing therapy can be defined as the process in which the client uses writing as a tool for self-expression and reflection, regardless of whether the client creates the writing himself or if a therapist or researcher recommends it to the client (Wright & Chung, 2001). It is distinguished by the use of writing as a therapeutic and developmental tool for the individual. Since initial research conducted by James Pennebaker, writing therapy has been found to have therapeutic benefits in elaborating traumatic situations (Pennebaker & Beall, 1986). In recent years, it has been shown

that writing that is both impressive and creative has good effects on the writer's physical and psychological health (Nicholls, 2009). Writing is used to create personal identity and purpose through the use of autobiographical writing in today's clinical practice, which has moved from a distress-focused approach to an educational one (Hunt, 2010). In this context, autobiographical writing is becoming an increasingly popular method that enables individuals to reflect on the course of their lives and gain a deeper understanding of the here and now (McAdams, 2008). It has also been observed that people generally tend to record major life events in their personal diaries, regardless of whether such experiences are positive or bad (Van Deurzen, 2012). A diary is a type of logbook in which specific entries such as thoughts, ideas, reflections, self-assessment and self-assurance statements are written. Journaling is a way of writing that encourages the writer to be more free. The difference between journaling and therapeutic writing is that in journaling, the writer is not given clear instructions on the topics and methodology to follow while writing as in therapeutic writing. Keeping a diary these days can also be done through online blogs and social networking sites (Facebook). A private and impromptu diary can then be made public using this method. Writing approaches are often included in speech treatments, as both procedures (speaking and writing) promote the organization, acceptance, and integration of memories in the process of self-understanding (Lyubomirsky et al., 2006). However, expressive writing has also been shown to be useful when used as a "stand-alone" therapy for the treatment of symptoms associated with depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Reinhold et al., 2018). For the treatment of traumatized individuals, a recent study has shown that enhanced expressive writing (also known as writing with planned interactions with a therapist) is as beneficial as regular psychotherapy. It was observed that expressive writing on its own without additional discussion with a therapist was only marginally lower than in talk therapy.

Keywords: *Psychological Therapy Methods, Human Psychology, Psychological Health, Psychological Therapy*

1. Introction

concluded that expressive writing can serve as an adjunctive technique in promoting mental health with little interaction with therapists (Gerger et al., 2021). According to the findings of a more recent study (Allen et al., 2020), the good effect of writing skills may be mitigated by individual differences such as dysfunctional attitude and personality type (ie, high levels of trait anxiety, avoidance, and social inhibition). In such cases, therapeutic writing can be even more beneficial as it eliminates the need for contact with the therapist or other patients in the practice. The purpose of this article is to present examples and a summary of primary psychotherapeutic therapies in which writing therapy plays an important role in the healing process. For example, a popular use is to encourage patients' capacity for self-observation through the use of a journal as part of normal cognitive behavioral therapy (Butler et al., 2006).

2. Understanding Traumatic Experiences

Writing is also used in the therapeutic process of other traditional psychotherapies, such as the core application of writing to understand and overcome traumatic experiences; phenomenological-existential approach, in which writing has the function of giving meaning to events and explaining life goals (King, 2001); and acceptance and commitment therapy, where writing facilitates the thought-defusion process. Writing is also used in the therapeutic process of other traditional psychotherapies, such as the basic practice of writing to understand and overcome (Hayes, 2004). This review will also discuss the unique applications of the writing method in new psychological contexts, including positive psychotherapy, where the writing tool is used in a variety of productive approaches (for example, writing letters of gratitude or forgiveness). Smyth (1998) conducted a comprehensive analysis of thirteen case-controlled writing therapy studies, all showing the beneficial effect of writing techniques on one's psychological well-being. The benefits obtained as a result of writing activities such as developing self-regulation, clarifying life goals, gaining insight, discovering meaning and acquiring a new perspective can be classified as contributions to one's psychological and emotional health. Fredrickson's Broad and Build Theory of Positive Emotions (2004), writing can foster positive emotions. Because putting feelings and thoughts into words expands the scope of attention, opens different perspectives and

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makes the mind more flexible (King, 2001). In conclusion, we will discuss and explore the new contexts in which writing activities take place today, especially the internet and various social networks.

Clinical applications of writing therapy include the expressive writing method created by Pennebaker (Pennebaker & Beall, 1986), autobiography, and a diary in traditional cognitive behavioral therapy. These applications will be explained in more detail in the following sections.

He developed a technique he called expressive writing, which involves writing down one's feelings and thoughts as a way of overcoming traumatic experiences or situations that make one feel distressed (Pennebaker & Chung, 2007). As part of their first writing project, Pennebaker and Beall (1986) asked fifty college students to write for fifteen minutes each day for four days. They were given the task of randomly writing about either painful subjects or unemotional things. Writing about traumatic events was associated with fewer health center visits, as well as improvements in both physical and mental health, the study found. The experiment was conducted multiple times with different samples, including both people suffering from physical and mental pathologies such as depression and people suffering from physical diseases such as asthma and arthritis (Gortner et al., 2006). We looked at people with varying degrees of education and writing experience, but none of these factors mattered in our analysis. Initially, the study focused only on traumatic experiences; however, as time went on, researchers expanded their scope to include specific experiences as well as general emotional formations (Pennebaker & Evans, 2014). According to Pennebaker, the author's free acknowledgment and acknowledgment of their feelings is what makes writing therapeutic. As a result, the author is able to express their blocked feelings and create a story that has meaning for them.

Other therapeutic components of expressive writing,

(1) the ability to relate different events in one's life, and

(2) is the expansion of one's capacity for introspection.

The first interpretation may be preferred using causal terms such as "because", "cause" and "effect", while the second interpretation is "thinking", "knowing", etc. It can be preferred by using

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insight words such as These mental and emotional processes were analyzed using a computer program (Pennebaker et al ., 2015), and the results showed that the more patients used causality words in their writing, the more benefit they were from effectiveness.

The use of specific causal statements reflects the amount of cognitive elaboration of the event the patient has achieved and may suggest that the patient has successfully processed and integrated the emotional experience (Pennebaker et al ., 2003). an emotional event, the acquisition of insight into the event, the organization and integration of the upheaval in one's life path are therefore sources of the benefits of writing. Numerous studies have shown that first- or third-person writing changes the emotional tone of the story . [Citation needed] (Seih et al., 2011). It is common for people who have experienced a severe traumatic event to initially describe it in the third person. Later, when their elaboration and integration processes are in motion, they can recount their experiences in the first person. This is because it takes time for them to fully process what happened to them. The reason for this phenomenon is that while writing in the third person makes the author feel more secure and disconnected from the experience, writing in the first person reminds them that they are the protagonist of the traumatic event. While it is easier to write about a terrifying experience in the third person immediately after the event, research has shown that writing in the first person is more beneficial when it comes to elaboration (Slatcher & Pennebaker , 2006). Pennebaker and Evans (2014) examined a range of trauma -related issues; one was the distinction between talking and writing about traumatic experiences. When it comes to impressive writing, one of the most important components is to have the mindset that it can be completely candid and free to write about anything in a safe and private environment without necessarily having to share the content with an audience. On the other hand, discussing traumatic experiences requires the presence of an audience, and the most important factor is the listener's capacity to comprehend and accept the patient's story . Additionally, individuals with high levels of social inhibition and trait anxiety may find their interactions with therapists particularly challenging (Allen et al., 2020).

Because putting one's feelings and thoughts into words has a very beneficial effect, writing is often recommended as a healthy coping mechanism to deal with the challenges one faces in life. This is what makes all these treatments similar. The act of creating stories and thinking about the different

ways they can be retelled has the potential to highlight the potential for real change to happen on the one hand and the active role played by the individual on the other (Sandstrom & Cramer , 2003). Putting negative feelings into words can ignite seeking solutions, which can result in having a positive attitude towards life challenges and promoting personal growth. Writing can also be defined as an endurance process in this way.

Writing can have a wide variety of beneficial consequences, but there are cases where it may not be effective or lead to undesirable results. An example of this situation is when a person has to deal with problems that cause intense and painful emotions, for example. In such cases, writing can lead to emotional distress such as crying, a very low mood, and even collapse (Pennebaker & Chung, 2007). Analyzing a traumatic event has the potential to initiate a process known as cognitive rumination , which is one of the specific symptoms of post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Pennebaker & Evans, 2014). In summary, the expressive writing technique is widely used in patients with traumatic conditions.

Writing about traumatic experiences can be helpful in elaborating the negative emotions associated with turmoil, constructing a narrative of the event, and giving meaning to it. Writing about traumatic experiences can also help give meaning to the event. However, if a client's discomfort levels are really high and/or sustained by cognitive rumination , they are not recommended to participate in a writing activity.

Writing therapy has also been shown to be beneficial in the process of developing a person's sense of self (Cooper, 2014). Dan McAdams , an important pioneer of this method , developed an identity life history model. This model assumes that individuals create and tell life narratives that evolve as a way of providing purpose and integrity to their lives. McAdams' model was an important step in the development of this method (McAdams , 2008).

3. Recreating the Past Using Narrative Identities

Identity is an internalized narrative that consists of many different elements of a story , such as setting, plot, character (or characters), and theme(s). In fact, human lives move through time and

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space, have a large supporting cast as well as a main character, and are shaped by a variety of overarching ideas. Using narrative identities, one can re-enact the past, become aware of the present, and have a perspective on the future. People tell themselves stories to make sense of their lives, and these tales help them understand who they are, who they are, and who they might be based on their self-perception and social identity.

For example, a biography is a written history of a person's life; It is about reconstructing a personal story in which important events are chosen and told. Biographies can be divided into several categories. The process of selecting key moments from a person's life to highlight the transformative potential of biographies is called "event selection" (Lichter et al., 1993).

Similarly, an autobiography can serve as a tool for the creation of a written biography. The first benefit of using autobiographical narratives as a form of therapy is the opportunity to better define one's sense of identity. This can be achieved by recognizing and giving meaning to significant personal changes. According to Bruner (2004), getting the client to write their autobiography enables them to accept that they are the ones writing their experiences (a sense of personal agency). People often erroneously remember details of events that occurred in the past, as time passes or because they are affected by distortion mechanisms. Autobiography is a therapeutic medium as it stabilizes people's autobiographical memories (McAdams, 2008).

Autobiography is useful not only for codifying each event of the self-story, but also for integrating different experiences and analyzing the trace of life, emphasizing both continuity and changes. This is because autobiography is useful for integrating different experiences. McAdams explored the role that autobiography plays in the life-transformation process, using a written method he calls "Guided Autobiography" (McAdams et al., 2006). The aim of this approach to psychotherapy is to explore the link that exists between the uninterrupted flow of story themes and changes in the person's personality. In ten sessions, each lasting two hours and taking place once a week, participants are asked to reflect and describe the most important events in their lives related to a particular life theme (e.g. family, money, work) (Reker et al, 2014). Guided autobiography is an effective method that helps participants understand and appreciate their life stories, thus increasing their optimism and self-confidence.

As a result, the guided autobiography method developed by McAdams contains several therapeutic components. These components include emphasizing the process of continuity between these elements, as well as the ability to make connections between life events and personal memories. At the same time, major life changes are brought to light and the person has the opportunity to strengthen their sense of agency by gaining a better understanding of their role as the hero of one's own life. Therefore, guided autobiography has the potential to enhance both one's own well-being and a sense of purpose in life.

4. Early Stages of Cognitive Therapy for Depression

It requires a written exercise in which the client is asked to note when and where a stressful situation occurred, the automatic thoughts it elicits, associated emotions, and the resulting behavior. This technique was developed by Aaron Beck in the early stages of cognitive therapy for anxiety and depression (Beck, 1979). While writing this diary, authors learn to pay attention to their functions and gain self-awareness about their problematic issues (King & Boswell, 2019). According to the traditional CBT method, the therapeutic components of structured journal writing consist of helping clients increase their awareness of automatic thoughts and beliefs that affect their emotions and behaviors. The diary then allows for cognitive restructuring processes in which negative, automatic thoughts are analyzed and modified to obtain a more realistic attitude towards life events and problematic situations (Beck, 1979). Therefore, writing techniques in CBT consist of keeping a structured diary supervised by therapists throughout the various stages of the therapeutic process. The journal in CBT specifically aims to address symptoms and distress, but can also trigger cognitive changes, maturation, and improved self-awareness at the end of clinical work (Butler et al., 2006). Its principles assume that life always has meaning, even in the most adverse circumstances, and that people always try to find personal meaning in their existence (supposition of the will to meaning). From this perspective, the magazine can be thought of as a place where people find meaning in life-threatening events and transform implicit and negative experiences into meaningful and positive experiences. In fact, Logotherapy emphasizes the importance of words in creating meaning, and in this case writing techniques are particularly

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suitable for this task. The client is asked to describe negative life events using words and phrases that help him gain a sense of meaning and acceptance.

In phenomenological-existential psychotherapies, writing assignments are used to increase clients' awareness of their limitations and to create an opportunity to reflect on both life and death (Yalom , 1980).

In the writing exercise, the client is encouraged to think and write down what people will say in their memory. This task aims to clarify and stick to personal values. This allows individuals to determine the direction they want to give their lives and to verify whether they are truly acting towards those goals. The main difference between logotherapy and guided autobiography is based on the philosophical framework used in the existential approach, which is absent in the Mc Adams paradigm . Also, in logotherapy , the narrative topic can be narrowed down to a specific traumatic event, which need not include the entire personal biography. The therapeutic components of logotherapy , therefore, relate to the increase in life meaning and the possibility of reframing and processing existential issues such as death, evil, and trauma in the individual's life experiences.

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) focuses on the acceptance of the unchangeable and the integration of different interventions (including mindfulness strategies) to increase psychological resilience and foster an active attitude towards problematic issues (Hayes, 2004).). ACT is based on Relational Framework Theory, a rigorous cognitive analysis (Reese , 2013). This theoretical framework proposes that language and cognition enable people to learn to relate events under arbitrary contextual control. This framework specifically analyzes paradoxes, metaphors, stories , exercises, behavioral tasks, and experiential processes (Hayes, 2004). This approach worked on a particular mechanism called "Thought Segregation" (Hayes, 2004), which deals with one's ability to distance oneself from problematic thoughts.

Often, individuals cannot see problems because they are "fused" with them. Decomposition techniques allow the individual to step away from problems and see them from a more independent perspective (ie, helicopter perspective exercise). In this way, patients have the opportunity to

identify a problematic issue, accept it and find a way to live with it, which can reduce the level of suffering (Hayes, 2004). Therefore, the act of writing can be considered as a way to stay away from one's own thoughts and feelings so that one can change their behavior and life choices according to their own values and priorities. The first part of this article describes how the traditional use of writing techniques has been analyzed within different forms of psychotherapy. The next part of this review will describe the application of similar writing techniques within the framework of positive psychology. In particular, the use of expressive writing, journaling, or other structured writing techniques will be identified as ways to promote personal well-being, personal growth, gratitude, and generally positive emotions.

5. Positive Psychotherapy

Unlike the traditional deficit-focused approach to psychotherapy, Positive Psychotherapy aims to address it with a similar stance, symptoms, and strengths (Rashid & Seligman, 2018). Positive Psychotherapy uses writing techniques at various moments of the therapeutic process. For example, at the beginning of therapy, clients are asked to write a personal presentation in positive terms. This exercise is called “Positive Introduction” (Rashid, 2015). The importance of this exercise lies in the fact that when writing a self-presentation, clients highlight their positive traits and qualities and are able to remember and describe a particular event in which these strengths emerged.

Therefore, this initial writing assignment can improve patients' self-esteem and self-awareness of positive personal traits. In the middle phase of positive psychotherapy, therapists may recommend the “Positive Assessment” activity to their clients. It consists of thinking and writing down the hurts, bad memories and negative events that happened in their past and still affect their lives.

Clients are asked to reframe these negative events from the past and explore possible positive consequences in terms of meaning or personal growth. The final phase of therapy focuses on discovering and educating the individual's strengths. Recommended exercises at this stage include writing assignments such as “The Gift of Time” and “Positive legacy” where the therapist asks

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clients to write how they will be remembered by significant others and future generations. “Positive Legacy” focuses on the positive connotations of writing and is often associated with planning a “time gift event” that puts these positive traits into practice (Rashid , 2015).

This technique has similarities with logotherapy and the ACT inscription exercise, but in PPT the client is guided to highlight the positive aspects of their life and personal qualities.

In addition, Positive Psychotherapy also requires specific writing techniques dedicated to promoting certain positive emotions, such as gratitude, forgiveness, and wisdom, as described below. Gratitude is a feeling of appreciation for people or events (which can also be an impersonal source such as God or Nature) triggered by the perception of having obtained something useful from someone or something (Rashid & Seligman , 2018).

Written gratitude exercises can be divided into a Letter of Thanksgiving, a Thanksgiving Diary, and “Good and Bad Memories.” A Letter of Gratitude consists of writing and delivering a letter of gratitude to a person to whom the client has never sincerely thanked. This intervention aims to strengthen the client's relationships and increase their social well-being (Lambert et al., 2010).

Thanksgiving Diary , clients are asked to write down three good things that happened to them during the day (Rashid , 2015). Many studies have shown that thinking about gratitude memories in written form promotes well-being and increases positive mood, because writing allows one to shape positive experiences (Toepfer et al., 2012; Wong et al., 2018).

In fact, in gratitude writings individuals are more likely to express positive emotions and have a high level of insight, making gratitude letters or diaries a powerful tool for generating not only well-being but also health improvements (Jans-Beken et al., 2020).

The difficulties experienced in writing a gratitude letter are related to the interpersonal nature of this task, as being grateful to someone requires being dependent on that person, and this can create a sense of vulnerability that makes the writer feel uncomfortable (Kaczmarek et al, 2015).

In this way, the psychological cost of writing a letter of gratitude is greater than expressing it in a private journal. Another important difference concerns the delivery of the letter, since while the letter is written to be delivered to someone else, the gratitude journal has a personal use. The main

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risk of writing a letter to someone is the possibility of not being accepted or judged by the reader. Therefore, recently, positive therapists may ask their clients to write the letter without having it delivered to the recipient. Thus, the benefits associated with a gratitude letter exercise are not necessarily linked to the act of delivery, but are embedded in the writing itself (Rash et al., 2011). Psychotherapy is a general term used to describe the process of treating psychological disorders and mental distress using verbal and psychological techniques. In this process, a trained psychotherapist helps the client deal with specific or general problems, such as a particular mental illness or source of life stress. A wide variety of techniques and strategies can be used, depending on the approach the therapist uses. Almost all types of psychotherapy involve developing a therapeutic relationship, establishing communication and dialogue, and working to overcome problematic thoughts or behaviors. Psychotherapy is increasingly seen as a separate profession in its own right, but clinical psychologists offer many different types of professionals, including psychiatrists, counselors, marriage and family therapists, social workers, mental health counselors, and psychiatric nurses.

therapist to improve how you function in your relationship (This approach allows group members to offer and receive support from others, as well as practice new behaviors within a supportive and receptive group). Best Online Therapy Programs We've tried, tested, and written unbiased reviews of the best online therapy. Programs like Talkspace, Betterhelp, and Regain. Techniques When people hear the word "psychotherapy," most people imagine the stereotypical image of a patient lying on a couch, with a therapist sitting in a chair nearby and jotting down thoughts on a yellow notebook. The truth is that there are a variety of techniques and practices used in psychotherapy. The exact method used in each case may vary depending on several factors, including the therapist's education and background, the client's preferences, and the precise nature of the client's current problem. Here is a brief overview of the main types of therapy. Behavioral Therapy As behaviorism became a more prominent school of thought in the early twentieth century, conditioning techniques began to play an important role in psychotherapy. Although behaviorism is not as dominant as it once was, many of its methods are still very popular today. Behavioral therapy often uses classical conditioning, operant conditioning, and social learning to help clients change problematic behaviors. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy The approach known as cognitive

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behavioral therapy (CBT) is a psychotherapeutic treatment that helps patients understand the thoughts and feelings that influence behavior. CBT is used to treat a number of conditions including phobias, addiction, depression and anxiety. CBT includes cognitive and behavioral techniques to change negative thoughts and maladaptive behaviors. The approach helps people change the underlying thoughts that contribute to distress and change the problematic behaviors that result from those thoughts. Cognitive Therapy The cognitive revolution of the 1960s also had a major impact on psychotherapy practice, as psychologists began to focus more and more on how human thought processes affect behavior and functioning. For example, if you tend to see the negative aspects of every situation, you will likely have a more pessimistic outlook and a more gloomy mood overall. The goal of cognitive therapy is to identify the cognitive distortions that lead to this type of thinking and replace them with more realistic and positive ones. By doing this, people can improve their mood and overall well-being.

Today, aspects of this approach are widely used. The humanistic approach to psychotherapy focuses on helping people maximize their potential and emphasizes the importance of self-discovery, free will, and self-actualization.

6. Psychoanalytic Therapy

Although psychotherapy was practiced in various forms up to the time of the ancient Greeks, it got its formal beginnings when Sigmund Freud began using talk therapy to work with patients . Techniques commonly used by Freud included transference, dream interpretation, and free association analysis. This psychoanalytic approach involves investigating a person's thoughts and past experiences to explore unconscious thoughts, feelings, and memories that may influence behavior.

7. Conclusion

There are many different types of psychotherapy available. The type that is best for you depends on several factors, including your preferences, condition, and severity of your symptoms . When

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children are young, it is common for therapy to involve the parent. Sometimes therapists work alone with parents. Older children may also see a therapist alone. Some types of therapy involve working with the whole family or other important adults in the child's life (for example, a teacher). Parent-focused approaches typically mean that parents talk to the therapist about their child's behavior and feelings. Psychological therapy with children may involve talking, playing, or other activities to help the child express their feelings and thoughts. Therapists may also observe parents and children together and then make suggestions for finding different ways to react. Psychological therapy for children can be done individually or in groups. Sometimes, a combination of therapies is most effective for helping a child .

With stress, anxiety, and depression at epidemic levels worldwide, therapy has become more common. Therapy is available in schools, hospitals, and even churches. Many modalities are finding preventative treatment to be helpful in preventing high-risk behaviors (Singla , 2018). To help spread good therapy practice, this article lists popular therapy interventions, must-have skills, and techniques you can use in your practice. Before we continue, we thought you might like to download our three Positive Psychology Exercises for free.

These science-based exercises will explore key aspects of positive psychology such as strengths, values and self-compassion, and will provide you with the tools to enhance the well-being of your clients, students or employees.

therapy that emphasizes reconciliation with aspects of one's life that are beyond their control, while at the same time emphasizing integrating various therapeutic approaches (such as mindfulness-based techniques) with one's self-development goals . psychological adaptability and fostering a determined stance against challenging issues (Hayes, 2004). Analytical Cognitive Therapy or ACT relies on a rigorous cognitive analysis known as Relational Framework Theory (Reese , 2013). According to the principles of this theoretical framework, the capacity of humans to learn to connect events subject to arbitrary contextual influence is provided by human language and cognition. Paradoxes, metaphors, fables, exercises, behavioral difficulties and experience processes are specifically analyzed using this paradigm (Hayes, 2004). This method has focused its attention on a particular process called "Thought Segregation" (Hayes, 2004), which explores

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an individual's capacity to emotionally separate himself from disturbing ideas. Oftentimes, people "melt" with the problems at hand and as a result they are unable to perceive them. Discrimination procedures provide the person with the ability to put some space between themselves and the problems at hand, and to see the problems from a more objective perspective (ie, the helicopter perspective exercise). Patients will have the opportunity to recognize, come to terms with, and develop strategies for coping with a difficult situation that has the potential to reduce the suffering they experience (Hayes, 2004). Therefore, the act of writing can be seen as a technique of avoiding one's own ideas and feelings so that one can adjust their actions and life choices according to their beliefs and priorities. The first part of this article examines the many ways in which the traditional use of writing strategies has been studied within various types of psychotherapy. The next section of this review will discuss how comparable writing strategies can be used in the context of positive psychology. Specifically, the use of expressive writing, journaling, or other organized writing approaches will be described as strategies to improve personal well-being, personal growth, gratitude, and generally pleasant feelings.

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